

GEOELECTRIC MEASUREMENTS FOR FAULT DETECTION IN BUCHAREST. CASE STUDY: BOTANICAL GARDEN

Diacopolos Constantin, Stochici Rasvan, Visan Madalina

Institute of Geodynamics, Romanian Academy, Romania

INTRODUCTION

Geophysical measurements regarding fault detection in the Bucharest area have a complex objective, which takes into account more the geological and tectonic structure of the Bucharest area.

The results show that it is useful to use the geoelectric method in detecting faults or other geological structures, especially since this method is easy to use. Electrometric methods offer the highest applicability for detecting and mapping depth resistivity anomalies (Ioane et al, 2016).

The investigations were carried out in the western part of the Botanical Garden, where the most problems were reported (infiltration in the foundation of a building, cracks in the foundation and in the alleys), where or they realized 6 profiles that could highlight a system of micro-faults, fractures.

METHODS AND RESULTS

The apparent resistivity measurements (ρ_a) were carried out for a set of distances AB, generally keeping the MN distance of 3 m and the central position of the measuring device.

For each length AB, a difference in electrical potential was measured between points M and N, created by injecting into the ground through electrodes A and B a current of 20 mA. The IntV3 Resistor was used to perform the geoelectric measurements (VES), using the Schlumberger type device. At the Botanical Garden were made 6 profiles (Fig. 1) of Vertical Electrical Surveys with different lengths of the AMNB device.

On the lithological section of Fig. 2 we can the presence of unconsolidated permeable porous rocks. In the depths there is still an alternation of clays and sands (layer wash). This is the proof that conductive horizons appear near surface on the resistivity section.

Fig. 1 Location of profiles

Fig. 2 Geotechnical drilling, Source: S.C.METROUL S.A

VES DATA INTERPRETATION

Following the interpretations of the VES data, a section of apparent resistivity was obtained for each profile, which shows the distribution of the resistivity in depth. Different resistivity resistances can be observed which give an overview of the geological structures.

It is observed on the geoelectric section from profile 1 (Fig. 3) resistivity contrasts, which can be interpreted to be tectonized areas, and geological formations characterized by low resistivity values (8-12 Ohm m), are interpreted as permeable porous rocks. conductive to fluid circulation. The geosection in profile 1, reflect an alternation of unconsolidated permeable porous rocks. In depth rocks come in contact with resistive compact rocks. The boundary between the two horizons is characterized by cracks and fractures (tectonized area) favourable for fluid circulation.

Fig. 3 Geoelectrical section profile 1

CONCLUSIONS

The geoelectric measurements highlighted the apparent resistivity contrasts, giving useful information to highlight and locate the geological structures in the respective area.

On the apparent resistivity sections obtained from VES measurements, there are significant resistivity contrasts that can be interpreted as tectonic areas. We have identified several types of anomalies, there is the possibility that some anomalies may be influenced by anthropic activities, others related strictly to the geological environment.

REFERENCES

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